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The Influence of Impressionism on Yan Wenliang's Landscape Oil Paintings and the Formation of His Style

Fu Chunxiao

Abstract

Yan Wenliang's artistic journey in landscape oil painting was notably influenced by Impressionism, highlighting his relentless pursuit of a fusion style that blends Chinese and Western elements. In the initial phase, Yan Wenliang focused on meticulous depiction and profound harmonious tones, reflecting the characteristics of the customs for oil paintings that mirrored the atmosphere of life during the Republic of China era. As his experience studying in France accumulated and his oil painting skills improved, his Impressionist style in landscape oil paintings gradually matured. In the later stage, Yan Wenliang's landscape oil paintings distinctly demonstrated a pursuit of individuality. During this phase, he exhibited a deep knowledge and integration of Chinese traditional aesthetics and Impressionism, conveying the aesthetic tastes of Chinese painters and profound emotions towards life.

Key Words

Yan Wenliang, landscape oil painting, Impressionism, Sino-western integration

Yan Wenliang was born in 1893, at the end of the Qing Dynasty, when French Impressionism was in its heyday. By the late nineteenth century, Impressionism played a revolutionary role in the history of Western art, with outstanding representatives such as Claude Monet, Pierre-Auguste Renoir, Camille Pissarro, Edgar Degas, and Alfred Sisley. These Impressionist masters left their studios to immerse themselves in nature, applying the principles of color science to plein air painting, capturing the immediate changes in light and color at different times and under various weather conditions, and demonstrating the independent spiritual expression of the artists. They captured the unpredictable, delicately shimmering light and color on the canvas, making the oil painting colors vibrant.

During the late Qing Dynasty and the Republic of China period, when Yan Wenliang's art was maturing, Impressionism had already been developing for half a century, and its scientific value in studying outdoor light was widely recognized. The widespread dissemination of Western painting in China facilitated Yan Wenliang's acceptance of Impressionist color expression. He not only absorbed the color expression methods of Impressionism

but also combined them with the artistic conception of traditional Chinese painting. He independently developed oil painting pigments and conducted in-depth explorations of color practice and theory, becoming an outstanding innovator in the early development of Chinese oil painting.

A thorough study of the influence of Impressionism on Yan Wengliang's landscape oil paintings and the formation of his fusion of Chinese and Western artistic styles, analyzing the evolution of his artistic style, systematically exploring the impact of Impressionism on his landscape oil paintings, and how he integrated Impressionist style with realistic oil paintings with traditional Chinese artistic conception, will not only help to deeply understand his unique contributions and far-reaching influence in artistic creation but also constitutes a highly valuable research subject.

1. First Impressions of Impressionism before Studying in France

Yan Wenliang was born into a family rich in artistic atmosphere, his father being a disciple of Ren Bonian,

a giant of Chinese painting in the late Qing Dynasty. From a young age, Yan Wenliang was influenced by art, developing a deep interest and passion for painting. In the early years of the Republic of China, with the introduction of European painting, various art forms such as Dian Shi Zhai Pictorial and monthly calendar paintings began to spread in China. The painting style of Impressionism also entered China through different channels, having an unprecedented artistic impact on young artists at the time, including Yan Wenliang, and leaving a distinct mark on his path of artistic exploration.

In 1909, following his father's command, Yan Wenliang was admitted to the Shanghai Commercial Press as a technical apprentice. The two-and-a-half years he spent in the copperplate and painting departments profoundly shaped his artistic path. At the Shanghai Commercial Press, Yan Wenliang learned the skills of plate making and practiced the creation of Western prints. The precision and rigor of print art, as well as the requirement for the meticulous depiction of small-sized works, had a profound impact on the formation of his delicate painting style and his preference for small works. During this time, he focused on studying the subtle changes in light and shadow on different objects, often using everyday items such as teapots, shoes, and umbrellas as subjects for sketching in his studio, capturing every detail of light and shadow with exquisite skill. This high sensitivity to changes in light and shadow and meticulous observation of the form of objects subsequently laid a solid foundation for Yan Wenliang to absorb the style of Impressionist oil painting.

After completing his apprenticeship at the Shanghai Commercial Press, Yan Wenliang returned to his hometown of Suzhou, focusing on studying Western oil painting. His works created with homemade oil materials, such as *Shihu Chuan Yue*, *Tianping Chu Xia*, *Flying Boat*, and the sixteen watercolor landscape paintings he painted for the Shanghai Laiqing Pavilion Bookstore became his representative works before he studied in France. These works demonstrated his precise grasp of perspective in the picture, his meticulous observation of objects under sunlight, and preliminarily revealed his absorption of the Impressionist technique of capturing changes in light and color. The rich Chinese cultural heritage reflected in these works showed Yan Wenliang's deep feelings and cultural cognition for his hometown. Especially in *Tianping Chu Xia*, Yan Wenliang depicted the water surface, trees, buildings, and other elements in meticulous detail as well as exquisite treatment of light and color, showing his deepening understanding of unified light sense. He used precise and vivid brushstrokes to capture the changes of trees under sunlight, capturing the true emotions of that

moment. The contrast of light and shade and the scenes full of life in *Tianping Chu Xia* appear vivid and lively under the rendering of light and color. In addition, Yan Wenliang tried different oil painting brushstrokes from thin to thick in these works, expressing his understanding and pursuit of light and color through the meticulous depiction and color treatment of the sky, buildings, etc. Through the changes of color, he conveyed his deep feelings for the depicted objects, showing his profound skills in form and color expression.

The works of Yan Wenliang during this period, in terms of modeling, followed the artistic footsteps of the masters of classical painting in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, while his use of light and color had already shown the stylistic characteristics of Impressionism. Although he had not yet had the opportunity to experience the demeanor of these masters in Europe, he reinterpreted scenes around him that were full of life from a unique Eastern perspective, close to nature, rich in Eastern style. These works laid an internal connection for his in-depth integration with Impressionist oil painting during his later study in France and laid a solid foundation for his artistic growth.

With the advice and help of Xu Beihong, Yan Wenliang went to study in France. On the way to France, he completed five small oil paintings full of Impressionist light and color characteristics, including *Saigon, Vietnam*, *Bird's Eye View of Hong Kong*, *Night Navigation in the Indian Ocean*, *Morning in Djibouti of the Red Sea*, and *Anchorage in Sri Lanka*. Due to the limitations of time and conditions, these works were all completed in one go, retaining a rich sense of improvisation. Apart from the first work, the other four take the sky and the sea as the theme. Without the interference of complex objects, Yan Wenliang was able to concentrate on observing and capturing the changes in light and shadow caused by time and climate. Whether it was the gray-blue shadows of clouds and moon at night, the milky yellow haziness of the fog at dawn, or the blood-colored twinkling of the waves at sunset, he strove to capture the fleeting beauty of light and shadow with concise brushstrokes.

2. In-depth Exploration of Impressionism during Studies in France

In 1928 Yan Wenliang went to France for further study, where he received a systematic academic art education at the École Nationale Supérieure des Beaux-Arts in Paris under the tutelage of Professor Ernest Roux. Although Professor Roux was a representative of the academic school, his early friendship with the neo-impressionist painter Georges Seurat inevitably influenced his painting

style, indirectly influencing Yan Wenliang. During his studies in France, Yan Wenliang frequently interacted with Chinese students like Zhou Bi Chu, whom Impressionism deeply influenced, and this interaction positively propelled his artistic development. He mainly practiced sketching in the plaster studio and used his spare time to visit art museums in Paris, refining his skills by copying classic works. While delving into classical painting, Yan Wenliang also studied the color theory and expressive techniques of Impressionist oil painting, striving to capture the instantaneous changes of light and color in nature, pursuing the vividness and harmony of light and color in the picture.

Yan Wenliang did not merely pursue the visual effect of the picture but focused more on experiencing and expressing the true aesthetic feeling of natural light and color, striving to show the immediate changes of objects in the overall light and color atmosphere, making the works full of joy and vitality. His study experience in France profoundly influenced his artistic style. He once publicly stated that Impressionism had a particularly significant influence on him, especially in the use of color.

He appreciated the use of color in Impressionism. He integrated the characteristics of this school into his works, striving to capture the intuitive feelings of nature and achieve a perfect fusion of light, color, and emotion. In an interview, Yan Wenliang mentioned “Originally I was against Impressionism, but now I do not oppose it, now I like Impressionism, so a person should be like this, otherwise there is no progress”¹.

During his studies in France, Yan Wenliang created several small oil paintings through outdoor sketching, all completed in one go, preserving the freshness of the initial creation. Many of his works took the sky and waves as the theme, capturing the beauty and true emotions in the changes of light and color, and recording the effects of light and color with simple brushstrokes. Despite the limitations of objective conditions Yan Wenliang still achieved the creative pursuit of Impressionist painters, creating sketch works with Impressionist characteristics, and continued to focus on landscape oil painting, capturing the changes of light and color. In addition, Yan Wenliang's painting skills also brought him closer to Impressionism. In his early work,

Figure 1. Yan Wenliang. *Port in Sri Lanka*, Oil on canvas, 17×25cm, 1928..

Figure 2. Yan Wenliang. *Florence Square*, Oil on canvas, 16×24 cm, 1930.

before studying in France, he had already used the technique of color decomposition and juxtaposition in his works, creating effects through visual mixing at a certain distance. Yan Wenliang's artistic path oscillated between the realism of Gustave Courbet and the Impressionism of Monet, Pissarro, and Sisley. At the time, he did not fully realize that these two artistic schools deeply influenced him. He once said: "Regarding Impressionism, I didn't like it then, but Impressionism unconsciously influenced me. The color of Impressionism is good. At that time, I only knew that I wanted to paint realistically. Sometimes, I painted a picture quickly, and people said I was Impressionist."² These straightforward words indirectly reflected Yan Wenliang's painting concept, and his works are the most powerful proof of this concept. Impressionism is committed to truly recording the scenery of the moment, promoting the development of realism from the dimension of color. Yan Wenliang was good at landscape oil painting and integrated the capture of light and color by Impressionism into his pursuit of realism.

Nineteen thirty marked the peak of Yan Wenliang's sketching and creation during his studies in France. In

May, he traveled to Italy for more than twenty days with Liu Haisu, Sun Fuxi, Yang Xiutao, and Wu Hengqin. Under the sunshine of Italy, Yan Wenliang created fourteen landscape oil painting sketches during his three-week journey in Rome, Florence, Venice, Milan, and other places. Among them, works such as *Roman Ruins*, *Florence Square*, *Venetian Waterways*, *Venetian Palace*, and *St. Paul's Church in Venice* are particularly outstanding. They are full of the charm of Impressionist light and color, representing the peak of Yan Wenliang's overseas landscape oil painting sketch creation. These works have bright colors, distinctive regional characteristics, smooth creative techniques, vivid images, vitality and freedom, and a strong sense of the scene. Although the sizes are not large, each one is complete, reaching high levels artistically, and becoming outstanding representatives of Chinese oil painting in the first half of the twentieth century.

At the end of 1931 due to Yan Wenliang's study in France, and the chaos in the management of Suzhou Art School which relied on his leadership during his three years of studying abroad, he urgently needed to return to China to continue his work. Yan Wenliang chose to return

Figure 3. Yan Wenliang. *Berlin Old Palace*, Oil on canvas, 17×25 cm, 1931.

to China by train, making a brief stop in Berlin for two days, during which he painted *Berlin Old Palace*, marking the end of his overseas study of landscape oil painting sketch creation. *Berlin Old Palace* has gorgeous colors, full of Impressionist characteristics, and is entirely based on the feeling of sketching from the scene. Yan Wenliang disliked affectedness and opposed “processing after returning home.” He once clearly stated “For sketching from the scene, the tone is easy to grasp, but processing after returning home is easy to mess up. Because one is from sketching, the second is that even if it is processed, it must be processed according to the scene. Processing at home is artificial, and making as few changes as possible is better”³.

The many works created by Yan Wenliang during his study in France from 1928 to 1931 show the gradual maturing of his Impressionist style. Influenced by Impressionist oil painting, he focused on the expressiveness of color, pursued the changes of natural light and color, captured the beauty of nature, and applied the color theory and techniques of Impressionism in his works, pursuing the sincere emotions in the changes of light and color, creating a harmonious beauty of light and

color in the picture, showing his mastery of the treatment of light and color and the subtle changes of color, and presenting a fresh, bright, and vibrant Impressionist style. Yan Wenliang's works not only focus on the relationship between light and color but also emphasize the direct experience of nature, presenting a variety of colors completely on the canvas, producing an interactive effect of light and color, form, and emotion, showing the authenticity and realism of the Impressionist style. Yan Wenliang integrated the elements of Impressionism into his creation, and his understanding and expressiveness of light and shadow, color, and natural beauty gradually deepened.

The overseas landscape oil paintings created by Yan Wenliang during his study in France from 1928 to 1931, although not large, better reflect his artistic achievements and the peak in his artistic career. Now it seems that these works are the purest in artistic exploration; whether in the use of color or perspective structure, Yan Wenliang's sketch works at that time were excellent, marking his comprehensive mastery of oil painting techniques, without any stiffness. Therefore, his works during his study in France have significantly contributed to modern

Chinese oil painting history.

3. After Returning from Studies in France: Synthesis of Eastern and Western Styles

For nearly twenty years—from 1931 after returning from studying in France until the great changes in Chinese society and politics in 1949 and including the eight years of resistance against Japan—Yan Wenliang mainly devoted himself to running the Suzhou Academy of Fine Arts. The accumulation of Chinese culture during this period undeniably influenced him.

Yan Wenliang's Impressionist-style landscape oil paintings continued for the first few years after his return to China. In 1934, Yan Wenliang and the teachers and students of Suzhou Academy of Fine Arts went to Putuo, Zhejiang, for travel and sketching and he painted eight works, including *Tide Cave*, *Front Temple Hall*, *Putuo Market Street*, *Putuo Paradise*, *Putuo Front Temple*, *Putuo*

Mountain Gate, *Distant View of Buddha's Top Mountain*, and *Thousand Steps Beach*. Among them, *Putuo Market Street* and *Putuo Paradise* reflected the painter's keen sensitivity to the light and color of Impressionism, with thick and viscous colors, decisive and powerful brushstrokes, accurately and vividly capturing the grayness of the air in the Jiangnan area of China.

After the founding of the People's Republic of China in 1949, with the signing of the *Sino-Soviet Treaty of Friendship, Alliance, and Mutual Assistance*, there was a tendency for the Chinese painting world to fully "Sovietize". The realistic aesthetic expression advocated by the former Soviet Union coincided with Yan Wenliang's advocacy that "individual art should be based on realism, to express the truth and beauty in nature and society, to make people happy and beneficial to their body and mind, and to promote the progress of human society"⁴.

While studying the formation of Yan Wenliang's landscape oil painting style during this period, the

Figure 4. Yan Wenliang. *Moonlight River*, Oil on canvas, 34×46.5cm, 1940..

proposal of the nationalization of oil painting in the Chinese painting world in the late 1950s, and the debate on how to treat Impressionist oil painting, should not be ignored. The extreme view that criticized Impressionism for “avoiding major social events, avoiding the contradictions and struggles between people in class society, and excluding the position of the working people in artistic creation”⁵ gradually gained the upper hand. The devaluation of Impressionism, mixed with some political needs at the time, was a rejection of other European painting styles and schools due to the one-sided Sovietization. This literary and artistic trend was unfavorable for Yan Wenliang, whom Impressionism had influenced while studying in France. Therefore, the situation also forced the change in his painting style. What is commendable is that in a series of excellent works that mark the formation of the painter's style the integration of Impressionist light and color and the expression of Eastern artistic conception is still reflected.

Yan Wenliang frequently embarked on journeys for on-site sketching, capturing the light and color in Chinese natural landscapes, recording the intuitive feelings and inner experiences at different times and places, and expressing his deep feelings for nature. Especially against the politically turbulent background of the 1950s and 1960s, he insisted on creating landscape oil paintings that did not involve political issues, which was particularly difficult at the time. For example, during his two visits to Beijing to attend the Cultural Congress in 1953 and 1960, he sketched and created a series of oil paintings such as *Temple of Heaven*, *Zhongshan Park*, *Yudai Bridge*, and *Summer Palace*. In addition to teaching in Suzhou, Shanghai, Hangzhou, and other places, he also painted works such as *Distant View of Xiling*, *Distant View of Geling*, *Three Ponds Reflecting the Moon*, and *Tiger Hill*. Of course, most of his works still depict the scenery around him, such as *Pujiang Dawn*, *Shanghai Bund*, *Suburban Scenery*, and *Shaoguang*. In works such as *Panoramic View of Chenghuang Mountain*, *Water City Gate*, *Suzhou Liuyuan*, *Nine Dragon Wall*, and *Dayu Mausoleum*, Yan Wenliang captured the changes of afternoon sunlight and color with unrestrained, fresh and natural brushstrokes, revealing the simplicity and depth of the works, reflecting his deep understanding of the natural and cultural characteristics of his hometown. Works such as *South Lake Sunrise*, *Pujiang Dawn*, and *Shanghai Bund* display his superb skills in depicting the changes of dawn and morning mist on the water with rigorous, meticulous, and vivid techniques. Works such as *Bedroom*, *A Corner of Home*, and *Shaoguang* focus on depicting family life scenes—every detail that he is familiar with and cherishes, from the tender green grass

to the fresh air to the morning light with dew coming through the windows; these works are not only visual arts but also reflect Yan Wenliang's longing and attachment to nature and life in his later years.

During this period, Yan Wenliang's creations also showed another trend: over-emphasizing the sketch relationship of the body and spending too much time on meticulous carving, which weakened his artistic enthusiasm and the immediate appeal of his works. Works such as *The 10th Anniversary of National Day*, *People's Avenue*, *Bumper Harvest of Fruits*, and *Contending Flowers* still show exquisite skills in detail, but they seem to lack some elements that can touch an audience's emotions and resonate in the whole. Yan Wenliang also realized this and once said, “Sometimes we lose something because we are too meticulous.”⁶ However, due to his personality and experience making prints in his early years, he found it difficult to get rid of this tendency. Singleness, rigidity, and triviality, to some extent, hindered him from reaching a higher level of purity, simplicity, and perfection. Moreover, with the increase of age, the degradation of senses, and the emergence of vision problems, this trend became increasingly obvious, gradually becoming a key factor affecting his later painting style.

If Yan Wenliang's works in the period with the most personal characteristics are regarded as achieving a harmonious unity between Impressionist light and color and Eastern aesthetics, then in his later years he emphasized the elements of Eastern aesthetics more. Each of his landscape oil paintings is like a thought-provoking image poem. In the peak period of Yan Wenliang's artistic career, his landscape oil paintings showed the clever integration of Impressionist light and color techniques and the spirit of Eastern art. However, in his later years, his works further integrated the philosophy and aesthetics of the East, making the Eastern connotation occupy a more prominent position in his paintings. These works are not only a display of visual art but also a poetic expression, each full of profound connotations and fascinating artistic conception.

During the Cultural Revolution, Yan Wenliang, like most artists, suffered from physical and mental torment, leaving the painter with many painful memories and bitter emotions. The accumulation of this kind of emotional suffering is crucial for forming the creative method of imagery light and color. Because of anger and creation, and the expression of emotions in the scene “ordering the wind and moon as slaves,”⁷ it is closer to the creative mode of Chinese painting and the essence of Chinese traditional culture. In May 1969, Yan Wenliang, who was “liberated,” was able to return to his former residence in

Xin Kang Garden on Huaihai Middle Road in Shanghai, avoiding the outside world, recalling, memorizing, superimposing, and combining the short scene fragments that passed by in a hurry but excited him, creating a series of landscape oil paintings like image poems. Of course, old age and difficulty in walking objectively prevented the painter from going out to sketch like a younger person to gain more new feelings. He lived in memories and created old dreams.

After the 1970s, Yan Wenliang's creations achieved a close interweaving of Impressionist and realistic styles and gave birth to works containing the essence of Chinese culture. These works not only reflect the Chinese nation's spiritual core and the artist's aesthetic feelings but also highlight his solid painting skills and mature artistic style, creating his unique artistic expression. In representative works such as *Sunny Report*, *Good Spring Light*, *Returning with the Moon*, and *Ode to the Motherland*, Yan Wenliang praised the brightness of spring, outlined a strong local flavor, and expressed his deep love and affection for the motherland's mountains and rivers. These works carry his relentless pursuit of the spirit of the Chinese nation, skillfully integrating Western fine realistic painting skills and Impressionist color in expressing the local national emotions while combining Impressionist style with rural themes, forming the artist's unique artistic expression and providing new directions and inspiration for the evolution of Chinese oil painting.

In the later years of Yan Wenliang's creative work, the colors became more vivid and dazzling, and the depiction of light and shadow and colors became more colorful, showing his keen insight and precise ability to capture light and color. At the same time, he integrated the Impressionist oil painting style and the poetic artistic conception in Chinese painting. He skillfully integrated the Impressionist oil painting techniques into his sketching creation, highlighting his profound cultural heritage and deep understanding of Chinese culture. This integration and innovative artistic technique not only show Yan Wenliang's in-depth exploration and exquisite expressive skills in light and color, but also show his deep concern and expression for local culture and national emotions. Works such as *Night Navigation on the Pu River* and *Snow Clearing* have become the hallmark of his style with their profound and perfect artistic realm and superb execution, showing his in-depth exploration of Eastern aesthetic taste. In *Night Navigation on the Pu River*, Yan Wenliang captured the fishing boats sailing at night with soft and dreamy brushstrokes, showing the instant impression of the Pu River and the fishing boats, creating a harmonious movement of light and color, presenting a perfect combination of Impressionism and

Eastern charm. Similarly, *Snow Clearing* also shows Yan Wenliang's exploration of light and color, reflecting the painter's sensitive capture of natural light and color and his deep understanding of Eastern aesthetic taste through a profound and perfect artistic realm and excellent skills. These works not only show the expressive power of Impressionist light and color in the use of color—capturing the changes of light and shadow in Chinese landscapes, recording the artist's intuitive feelings, and expressing a deep affection for nature—but also show Yan Wenliang's understanding and expression of his hometown's natural scenery and cultural temperament, bringing new ideas and forms to Chinese oil painting.

Yan Wenliang, from the age of eighty to ninety, still tirelessly pursued the promise of "painting until the last breath of life."⁸ He created a series of landscape oil paintings such as *Spring, Summer, Autumn, Winter, Good Spring Light, Sunset Illumination, Glory of the Motherland* and *Snow Scene*. Most of these works focus on the expression of poetry and the creation of artistic conception. They are closer to the unique temperament and talent of Chinese painters in terms of creative ideas, aesthetic psychology, and specific artistic expression and techniques. Yan Wenliang's works in his later years show us the unique aesthetic taste and values of the East, as if each painting has been engraved with the historical imprint of the Chinese nation for five thousand years.

Of course, in the 1970s, the painter was partially closed off. Works such as *A String of Red, Goose Coming Red, Sichuan Sunflower, Mao Jia Tang*, and *On the Way* still mainly focus on outdoor sketching, but due to his declining vision, the brushstrokes become bolder and rougher and the colors are more subjective. In the winter of 1985, when Yan Wenliang finished the last strokes of *Canglang Beauty* and *Canglang Summer Night*, it also marked the end of his artistic career of nearly ninety years. Starting from Canglang and returning to that starting point, the painter captured the green shades of Canglang that disappeared with dreams with his brush and echoed with his colors the summer night school songs that drifted with the wind. He always loved his Canglang and forever solidified and fixed this nostalgia, attachment, and persistence in his final brushstrokes.

Two years and six months after putting down the brush, Yan Wenliang's last light of life was exhausted.

4. Conclusion

Through integrating Chinese and Western artistic elements and pursuing a personal style, Yan Wenliang gradually formed a unique personal identity, adhering to the main theme of pursuing aesthetic beauty in his

Figure 5. Yan Wenliang. *Moon Shadows in Shihu*, Oil on canvas, 48×63 cm, 1982.

paintings. By deepening the concept of “truth, goodness, and beauty”, he developed a distinctive style, creating oil paintings that were well-received by the masses.

During his studies in France, Yan Wenliang absorbed the artistic concepts and techniques of Impressionism. After returning to China, he gradually formed oil painting artworks that had Impressionist characteristics and embodied the Chinese national sentiment. His works display different appearances in different periods, bravely breaking through existing painting forms, possessing the romantic temperament of a literati, and expressing the humanistic feelings pursued by the painter. Yan Wenliang applied the rigorous sketching and the richly varied colors of Impressionism to the national sentiments of the Chinese land, forming a unique artistic language. He made the greatest effort to integrate the language of Impressionist oil painting with the aesthetic psychology of the Chinese nation, creating works that better fit the aesthetic conception of the Chinese people with his Western painting techniques. From making his oil paints

to learning the focal perspective of the Renaissance period and the light and color expression of Impressionism, he always expressed the language of European painting in a way of understanding that is Chinese. His works are neither purely “national essence” grown locally nor purely “foreign goods;” rather, with the greatest effort to express the language of Western painting, they integrate the breath of Chinese traditional culture.

Yan Wenliang's landscape oil paintings reflect the exploration of Chinese cultural charm and the colors of Impressionist oil painting, conveying the aesthetic emotions of Chinese artists and the praising of life. He opened new realms for Chinese aesthetic concepts and laid the foundation for the widespread application of oil painting colors in China. Yan Wenliang's artistic achievements are not only in the establishment of his style and the exploration of the nationalization of oil painting, but also reflect his pursuit of the concept of truth, goodness, and beauty, as well as the expression of

humanistic feelings.

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FU CHUNXIAO (1992-), the female, graduated from the School of Art at Henan University with a Master of Arts degree, is currently a Ph.D. candidate in Arts at the Graduate University of Mongolia, a member of the Henan Artists Association, and has taught printmaking courses at Henan University and Shang-

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Editor: Li Congcong

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顏文樑風景油畫受印象派影響及其個人風格的形成

付春曉

摘要：顏文樑的風景油畫藝術成長的軌跡中，印象派對他產生了顯著的影響，並彰顯了其對中西融合風格的不懈追求。初始時期，顏文樑專注於精心刻畫和深沉諧調的色調，反映了民國時期生活氣息的風俗油畫特點。隨著留法求學經歷的積累和油畫技藝的提升，他的印象派風格油畫逐步變得成熟。進入後期，顏文樑的風景油畫明顯展現出對個性化的追求，在此階段，展現出他對中國傳統美學和印象派的深入研究與融合，也傳遞了中國畫家的審美情趣和對生活的深厚情感。

關鍵詞：顏文樑；風景油畫；印象派；中西融合